

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and
assessment of plastic pollution

First Year Report on Project Management Activities, Procedures and Tools

Date: 31.10.2021

Deliverable Identifier: D6.1

Document Version: 1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action under Grant Agreement No 101003805. The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the author and in no way reflects the views of the European Union.

Project Acronym:	EUROqCHARM
Project Full Title:	EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution
Grant Agreement no:	101003805.
Project Duration:	36 months (01/11/2020 – 31/10/2023)
Type of Action:	Coordination and Support

Document Control Information

First Year Report on Project Management Activities, Procedures and Tools	
Work Package Title	WP6 Project management and coordination
Deliverable title	D6.1 First Year Report on Project Management Activities, Procedures and Tools
Lead Beneficiary	NIVA
Lead Authors	Amy Lusher
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Submitted by	Amy Lusher
Deliverable due date	31 st October 2021
Actual date of delivery	31 st October 2021
Version	1.0

Review process:

Name	Role	Action	Date
François Galgani	WPL	Approve	28.10.2021
Stefano Aliani	WPL	Approve	28.10.2021

History of changes:

Version	Date	Short Description of Changes	Authors	Organization
0.0	27.10.2021	Draft circulated to WP Leaders	Amy Lusher	NIVA
0.1	29.10.2021	Draft modified after feedback	Amy Lusher	NIVA
0.2	29.10.2021	Formatting	Gabrielle Hairabedian	NIVA
1.0	30.10.2021	Version submitted to the EC	Amy Lusher	NIVA

Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report	x
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	

Dissemination level		
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
PU	Public	x

About EUROqCHARM

This deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action programme under Grant Agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

Plastic pollution has become a global environmental and societal concern in recent years. Numerous protocols have been developed to monitor plastic debris, but these are rarely comparable. This has hindered gathering of knowledge regarding pollution sources, development of monitoring programmes and risk assessments and implementation of mitigation measures. To develop long-term solutions to reduce plastic pollution, it is essential to establish harmonised methodologies. EUROqCHARM will address this by critically reviewing state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonisation one step further, validating them through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) study. This will bring together prominent laboratories in environmental plastics analysis and will produce certified reference materials to be marketed for at least three of the four target matrices (water, soil/sediment, biota, air), during and after project completion.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We will identify Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP will be validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level to decide if further validation is needed (by ILC).

Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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Executive Summary

Project management activities, procedures and tools were identified as key elements for smooth implementation of the EUROqCHARM project. A special effort has been made during the first year of the project to ensure these are properly developed, implemented and managed. The management activities, procedures and tools follow the guidelines established in the EUROqCHARM Project Handbook developed in the starting phase of the project within WP6 – Project Management and Coordination.

The first-year report provides an overview of all project management activities, procedures and tools developed and implemented during the period November 2020 – October 2021.

- The first section presents the general project management processes that ensures smooth coordination of activities resulting in high quality deliverables. This includes the project management structure and lists the different levels of organization, as well as persons responsible for the different roles defined within the management structures and procedures.
- The second section illustrates all management and coordination activities during the first year of the project. This includes both communication within and outside the consortium, listing good practices, templates etc. Having an internal communication strategy ensures clear and effective communication between the partners and allows for recognition of early escalation and timely resolution of management and technical issues. External communication, dissemination and exploitation processes ensure a unified presentation of the project to the public.
- The final section contains project management activities related to risk assessments.

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List of Abbreviations, Acronyms and Partner Codes

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCC	Communication and Coordination Committee
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSDP	Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan
DoA	Description of Action
FO	Financial Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
GEA	General Assembly
ILC	InterLaboratory Comparison
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Support
RAPs	Reproducible Analytical Pipelines
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee
SSAB	Stakeholders and Standardisation Advisory Board
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Acronyms	Definition
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ISO	International Organisation for Standards
JRC	Joint Research Council
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NORMAN	Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances
NEC	National Ethics Councils
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris Convention
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
TGML	Technical Group on Marine Litter
UN	United Nations

Partner code	Full partner name
NIVA	Norwegian Institute for Water Research
CNR-ISMAR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Scienze Marine)
VU	Free University Amsterdam (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam)
IFREMER	Institut Francais De Recherche Pour L'Exploration de la Mer
NIMRD	Institutul National de Cercetare-Dezvol Marine Grigore Antipa
SALT	-
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior Deinvestigaciones Cientificas
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research
ILVO	Flemish Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (Instituut voor landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek)
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz- zentrum fur Polar- und Meeresforschung
AU	Aarhus University
Chiron	-
EAWAG	Eidgenoessische Anstaly Fuer Wasserversorgung Abwasserreinigun und gew
OGS	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale
AFNOR	Association Francaise de Normalisation

1. EUROqCHARM Project Management, Execution and Procedures

EUROqCHARM is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project funded under the EC Horizon 2020 Programme which started in November 2020 and will run over three years. In order to reflect the complexity of the harmonisation procedures for plastic pollution monitoring and assessment, EUROqCHARM is structured into seven tightly inter-linked Work Packages (WP1-7). All WPs have strong relationships with one another, such that they can build on each other’s outputs and there are no stand-alone WPs. The project activities are distributed across 7 Work Packages (WPs), each one with a defined scope and objective (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The overall WPs structure of EUROqCHARM

1.1. Overview of Management Structure

The project management structure of EUROqCHARM has been designed to facilitate a smooth operation of the project from initiation to completion. As such, EUROqCHARM is organised based on the coordinating partner’s principles for project management and expanded to fit the specificities of a Coordination and Support Action. Thus, three different layers are considered – **Advisory Level**, represented by two advisory boards, **Strategic Level**, represented by Project Coordinator, Steering Committee and Communication and Coordination Committee, and **Operational Level**, represented by WP Leaders (Figure 2).

The project management roles established within EUROqCHARM include:

- The Project Coordinator (PC)
- A Scientific Project Manager (PM)
- Work Package Leaders (WPL)
- Task Leaders (TL)

Additionally, the following managing bodies hold fundamental roles:

- Steering Committee (SC)
- General Assembly (GEA)
- Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)
- Communication and Coordination Committee (CCC)
- Standardisation and Stakeholder Advisory Board (SSAB)

Figure 2. Management structure of EUROqCHARM

The three different layers and the responsibilities of each of the above bodies are briefly highlighted in the next section.

1.2. Strategic Level

1.2.1. Project Coordination Team (NIVA)

The **NIVA Management Committee** was established at the premises of the coordinating organization. It oversees the day-to-day operations and is responsible for the overall administrative, technical, financial aspects of the project management. The responsibilities of the Project Coordinator are shared by individuals with the main tasks as follows:

- Coordinate the implementation of the Work Packages activities (PC/PM)
- Promote effective communication between all participants
- Monitor progress of all participants and compliance with both the GA and the CA (PM)
- Ensure the day-to-day administration and financial coordination of the project (PM/PS, FO)
- Report all financial activity and information during the project duration (PC/PM/FPO)
- Monitor evolving risks (PC/PM)
- Act as end responsible for the technical periodic reporting (PM/PC)
- End responsible for the financial periodic reporting (FO)
- Communicate with the EC project officer (PC)
- Communicate with the EC financial responsible (PC/FPO)

The **NIVA Management Committee** includes members with valuable expertise, which cover the required competencies for the overall administrative, financial, scientific and technical aspects of EUROqCHARM:

Project Coordinator:

The Project Coordinator (PC) chairs the NIVA Management Committee. The PC has the overall responsibility for the progress of the Project including the smooth coordination of the administrative, scientific and financial aspects of the project. **PC: Bert van Bavel**

Scientific Project Manager:

The Scientific Project Manager (PM) ensures that the scientific and technical objectives of the project are met. The PM supervises the smooth implementation of the activities within and between WPs, coordinates the communication between WP Leaders (WPLs) and SABs regarding deliverables and monitors the progress towards continuous and periodic reporting. **PM: Amy Lusher**

Financial Officer (FO):

The Financial Officer ensures the financial coordination of the project including the overall reporting of project's financial activity. **FO: Ståle Mygland**

Project Support (PS):

Project Support ensures administration of the project, mainly by supporting the NIVA Management Committee, promoting effective communication between all project partners and supporting the project partners in utilization of the EUROqCHARM Microsoft Team. **PS: Liv Lang-Ree and Gabrielle Hairabedian.**

1.2.2. Steering Committee

The Steering Committee (hereafter SC) is the decision-making body within EUROqCHARM for all significant project issues (e.g., dissemination and exploitation plan, agreements on possible changes and adjustments in WPs, budget reallocation, etc.). The SC ensures the appropriate coordination with the corresponding boards at the advisory level and with the WPs at the operational level. The SC is responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly (hereafter GEA). SC actions rely on a consensus amongst its members. Members are responsible for monitoring the progress of EUROqCHARM to ensure that the project is in compliance with the DoA and if necessary, propose modifications to the GEA. Examples where the SC demonstrate their role:

- Technical and innovation aspects, exploitation, dissemination, commercialisation of the project
- Ensure effective day-to-day coordination and monitoring of the project
- Propose a plan for using and disseminating results to GEA
- Preparing press releases and joint publications by the Consortium or proposed by the Funding Authority

The SC is chaired by the PC with the assistance of the PM - who will be deputing the PC - who is responsible for preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing proposals for the General Assembly. The SC is formed by the PC, PM and WPLs (Table 1). Meetings are held quarterly, and at any time upon written request by 25% of the SC members.

Table 1. EUROqCHARM Steering Committee members

Role	Partner	Reference Person
PC /WP6	NIVA	Bert van Bavel
PM /WP7	NIVA	Amy Lusher
WP1 Leader	CNR-ISMAR	Stefano Aliani
WP2 Leader	VUA	Jacob de Boer
WP3 Leader	IFREMER	François Galgani
WP4 Leader	NIMRD	Elena Stoica
WP5 Leader	SALT	Joan Fabres

In the first year, the project meetings of the SC were held virtually through the EUROqCHARM Microsoft Team every two/three month on different themes aligned with the stage of the project implementation (Table 2).

Table 2. EUROqCHARM Steering Committee meetings in the first year of the project

Date	Theme	Attendees
28.01.2021	Project update, DMP status, WP status, Approval of CCC and Project Handbook for circulation	BVB, AL, SA, JdB, FG, ES, JF
29.04.2021	Project update, Plans for Annual Meeting, DMP status, WP status, Templates, SWOT workshop plans	BVB, AL, SA, JdB, FG, ES, JF
24.06.2021	Project update, Status of management activities, WP status, CCC update, Annual Meeting plans	BVB, AL, SA, JdB, FG, JF
28.10.2021	Project update, feedback from Annual Meeting, WP status, Deliverable update, Zenodo update	BVB, AL, SA, JdB, FG, JF

1.2.3. Communication and Coordination Committee

The Communication and Coordination Committee (hereafter CCC) was established in the first three months (Milestone 2) of the project to ensure appropriate coordination between the advisory level of the project (SABs, SSABS) and the operational level (WPs). The CCC has four permanent members as well as “hot” members which will join the CCC meetings on an “as and when needed” basis (Table 3).

The CCC is responsible for making sure the scientific objectives of the project are transposed into a variety of dissemination activities reaching out to the widest possible range of stakeholders beyond the project partners. The CCC is chaired by WPL 5- Joan Fabres. The core team plays a key role in the dissemination and communication activities between WPs, WPLs, Tls and project partners. It also includes the newsroom and responsibility for all social media. In the very first months after the project’s kick-off, the CCC team communicated mainly via email; with meetings on different topics aligned with the progress of the project held virtually through the EUROqCHARM Microsoft Team. Starting in August 2021, the CCC began routine monthly status meetings, with an increase in frequency when necessary (Table 4). The four permanent members of the CCC are represented by the PM, WP4 and WP5 Leaders as well as a representative from ILVO; the expertise of these four permanent members is complemented on an “as and when needed” basis with the one of additional knowledgeable partners.

Table 3. EUROqCHARM Communication and Coordination Committee members

Role	Partner	Reference Person
PM	NIVA	Amy Lusher
WP4 Leader	NIMRD	Elena Stoica
WP5 Leader	SALT	Joan Fabres
Partner	ILVO	Sofie Vandendriessche
“Hot” members	Will participate on an “as and when needed” basis.	

Table 4. EUROqCHARM Steering Committee meetings in the first year of the project

Date	Topic	Attendees
22.01.2021	EUROqCHARM Coordination and Dissemination	JF, BvB, AL
02.02.2021	EUROqCHARM Website Design Meeting	JF, SV, LP, BvB, AL
18.03.2021	Dissemination plan and publication schedule	JF, SV, AL
19.04.2021	Dissemination plan and publication schedule	JF, SV, AL
20.05.2021	EUROqCHARM Newsletter	JF, SV, LP, AL
31.08.2021	CCC Regular Status Meeting	JF, SV, GH, AL, BvB
28.09.2021	CCC Regular Status Meeting	JF, SV, GH, AL, BvB
14.10.2021	CCC Regular Status Meeting	JF, SV, GH, AL, BvB
28.10.2021	CCC Regular Status Meeting	JF, SV, GH, AL, BvB

Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan

During the first year of the project, the CCC developed the EUROqCHARM Communications Strategy and Dissemination Plan (CSDP) which is part of the Annual Reporting on Communication, Dissemination and Networking activities. In short, they set up a news and publication schedule for social media platforms.

Stakeholders' strategy

In the first months of the project, the CCC team has initiated the development of a stakeholder's engagement strategy, aimed at (i) facilitating the knowledge transfer and strengthening/enabling

capacity building on harmonized methods and standards for assessment and monitoring of plastic pollution, (ii) creating an international community, including diverse stakeholders’ groups that strive towards the harmonization of such methods and standards in a joint effort to tackle the plastic pollution.

The very first draft of stakeholders’ strategy covers aspects like: mechanisms and tools for stakeholders’ engagement, type of content and content appropriateness according to the stakeholder group involved, frequency and type of engagement expected from the various stakeholder groups mapped as relevant for the EUROqCHARM community.

1.2.4. General Assembly

The General Assembly (GEA) is the decision-making body for all the issues concerning matters not considered within the Annex I of Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement and comprises one representative by each Partner organisation. When a representative is unable to attend a GEA meeting, a substitute can be assigned by written agreement, and their voting rights are delegated to the substitute.

Veto rights by any partner are reserved for issues where fundamental interests of a partner are concerned. For minor decisions, the partners who are directly concerned are consulted by the partner requiring the decision; this in order to allow a smooth and easy project implementation.

The Project Coordinator (PC) chairs the General Assembly while the PM acts as rapporteur. The GEA management meetings are held to review the overall project progress, track Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and impact indicators, milestones and deliverables and review any technical or administrative issues. The GEA has the following decision powers:

- Approve major strategic decisions and the long-term detailed work plan of EUROqCHARM
- Approve the deliverables and technical report submitted to the EC
- Approve any requirements for modifications with WPs, and monitor progress of plans
- Review and/or amend the terms in the CA (i.e., additions or exclusion of partners)
- Agree upon proposals on defaulting parties

The GEA gathers at least once every year for *ordinary meetings* and can also convene *extraordinary meetings* at any time upon the written request of any member. Due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, the GEA meetings have been held virtually. Two GEAs were held in the first year of the project (Table 5).

Table 5. EUROqCHARM General Assembly meetings in the first year of the project

Date	Theme	Attendees
16.12.2020	Voting on roles and responsibilities: <i>Steering Committee, Scientific Advisory Board, Structure of Stakeholder and Standardisation Advisory Board, Brand Identity, Communication and Coordination Committee</i> ; Status of Project Handbook; Management procedures; Budget	All partners
21.10.2021	Voting on agreement to move a Deliverable 1.1 by 6 weeks – discussion of risk associated with this; Stakeholder mapping activity with all partners	All partners (with the exception of AU)

1.3. Operational Level

1.3.1. Work Package Leaders

WP Leaders (WPLs) supervise the activities within their Work Package (WP) and report the advances and unforeseen events to the NIVA Management Committee. EUROqCHARM contains the following seven Work Packages (WPs) as detailed in Table 6. Specifically, WPLs are responsible, limitedly to the Work Package of their competence, for:

- Management and monitoring of tasks and overall progress of the Work Package
- Formulating and implementation of a plan for all WP activities
- Executing planned activities
- Ensuring adequate quality of deliverables
- Technical soundness of developments
- Identification of possible risk(s) and reporting risk to the Steering Committee
- Participating in the Steering Committee
- Providing 6-month reports per WP (and a brief update of 3-month progress for Steering Committee reports)

Table 6. EUROqCHARM Work Packages

WP No.	WP Title	Lead partner	Participants	Start-End
WP1	Screening and analysis of existing methods and protocols for plastic pollution monitoring	CNR	NIVA, SALT, CSIC, NILU, ILVO, AWI, AU, Chiron, EAWAG, OGS, AFNOR	Month 1-15
WP2	Validation of methods for plastics analysis in environmental samples	VU	NIVA, VUA, IFREMER, CSIC, NILU, AWI, AU, Chiron, EAWAG, AFNOR	Month 3-36
WP3	Harmonisation: Integrate recommended procedures with policy, legislation and risk assessment	IFREMER	NIVA, CNR, IFRMER, NILU, ILVO, AWI, AU, EAWAG, OGS, AFNOR	Month 6-36
WP4	Capacity building	INCDM-NIMRD	NIVA, CNR, VUA, SALT, CSIC, NILU, AWI, AU, AFNOR	Month 24-36
WP5	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	SALT	NIVA, VUA, IFREMER, CSIC, NILU, AWI, AU, Chiron, EAWAG, AFNOR, ILVO	Month 1-36
WP6	Project management and coordination	NIVA	All	Month 1-36
WP7	Ethics requirements	NIVA	All	Month 1-36

1.3.2. Task Leaders

Task Leaders (TLs) are assigned with the coordination of separate tasks within Work Packages. TLs are responsible for implementing specific tasks and their deliverables (Table 7). TLs track technical and practical issues regarding the development of their tasks. Specifically, TLs are responsible for:

- Monitoring quality of deliverables and updating the corresponding WPL
- Identifying possible risks and reporting them to the corresponding WPL

Table 7. EUROqCHARM Tasks divided by Work Package

Task Number	Task Name	Delivery date	Lead partner
1.1	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in solid samples	Month 10	AU
1.2	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in aqueous samples	Month 10	AWI
1.3	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in biota samples	Month 10	ILVO
1.4	Identification of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines to analyse nano-, micro- and macro-plastics in air samples	Month 10	NILU
1.5	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) analysis of the identified methods	Month 15	CNR
2.1	Possibilities and needs to CRMs r plastic in solid, liquid and gaseous matrices	Month 6	VUA
2.2	Producing analytical standard candidate CRM, and candidate matrix CRMs	Month 36	Chiron
2.3	Organising one or more intercalibration studies using the candidate CRM with associated laboratories	Month 21	VUA
2.4	Statistical validation of the ILC results	Month 22	VUA
2.5	Feasibility study of the methods for monitoring studies in terms of analytical uncertainty, applicability and costs	Month 23	NIVA
2.6	Certification of reference materials	Month 36	VUA
3.1	Recommendations of most appropriate protocols and methods for monitoring programs	Month 25	AU
3.2	Identification of the most appropriate monitoring strategies	Month 31	IFREMER
3.3	Recommendation of standard measuring procedures for policy and legislation	Month 34	EAWAG
3.4	Synchronisation of European procedures on a global level and alignment with existing approaches and databases	Month 34	OGS
4.1	Operational network for Plastic Monitoring	Month 36	NIMRD
4.2	Capacity building for policy analysis and policy coherence	Month 36	NIMRD
4.3	Transnational Joint Actions	Month 36	NIMRD
5.1	EUROqCHARM brand identity: information and tools sharing through dedicated website and social media channels.	Month 36	ILVO
5.2	Organisation of the workshop with stakeholders on the results from WP	Month 17	ILVO
5.3	Organisation of the workshop with international laboratories participating in the quality control study	Month 19	VUA
5.4	Organisation of the workshop – “Sampling strategies for plastic litter (from macro to micro and nanoplastics) monitoring in the different environmental compartments”	Month 27	SALT
5.5	Coordinating collaboration with other ongoing activities	Month 36	SALT
5.6	Organisation of the EUROqCHARM Final conference	Month 36	NIVA
6.1	Project initiation, activity management and project work plan	Month 1	NIVA
6.2	Appointment of Scientific Project Manager, Steering Committee (SC), Communication and Coordination Committee (CCC)	Month 2	NIVA
6.3	Appointment of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)	Month 4	NIVA
6.4	Appointment of the Standardisation and Stakeholder Advisory Board (SSAB)	Month 6	NIVA
6.5	Administrative, financial and legal project management	Month 36	NIVA
6.6	Project management, coordination and communication	Month 36	NIVA
7.1	Ethics requirements	Month 36	NIVA

1.4. Advisory Level

1.4.1. Scientific Advisory Board

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) is instrumental in ensuring the achievement of all project objectives, the quality of the deliverables, dissemination and appropriate exploitation of the key outputs. The SAB is an advisory body who:

- Provides recommendation on scientific development of the project
- Provides consultation on selected project activities
- Validates results of the project at a high-level
- Provides critical input on activities of the project
- Provides input to identify developments and technologies of strategic interest
- Amplifies the dissemination and awareness of the initiative
- Contributes to the clustering process among the community of European stakeholders.

In the first months of the project implementation, each appointed member of the Scientific Advisory Board has been asked to sign an agreement (including a Non-Disclosure Agreement) that formally defines their tasks and responsibilities. Meetings are held annually so that the SAB can oversee the project’s developments and results. Ad-hoc meetings or email exchanges may be arranged if the PM or WPLs require input from SAB affiliated with specific WPs. The members of the SAB are listed in Table 8.

Table 8. EUROqCHARM Scientific Advisory Board members

Expert	Institute	WP interest
Chelsea Rochman	University of Toronto	WP 1, WP3.
Amy Urhin	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	WP1, WP2, WP3.
Daoji Li	East China Normal University	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4.
Richard Thompson	University of Plymouth	WP1, WP3, WP5.
Kevin Thomas	The University of Queensland, Australia	WP1, WP2, WP3.
Peter Ryan	FitzPatrick Institute of African Ornithology	WP1, WP3.
Alex Turra	USP – Universidade de São Paulo – Universidade pública	WP3, WP4, WP5.

1.4.2. Standardization and Stakeholders Advisory Board

The Standardisation and Stakeholders Advisory Board (SSAB) is instrumental in ensuring the achievement of all project objectives, the quality of the deliverables, and dissemination and appropriate exploitation of the key outputs. In the first months of the project’s implementation, each appointed member of the SSAB has been asked to sign an agreement (including a Non-Disclosure Agreement) that formally defines their tasks and responsibilities. Contact details of the SSAB members are held by WPL5 and PM.

Currently there are 17 members of the SSAB representing the following sectors, groups, categories and/or types: governmental, intergovernmental, industry, organisation, standardisation organisation, etc (see Figure 3). SSAB members are represented geographically within Europe (e.g., Norway, Denmark, Italy, and Germany), as well as internationally (e.g., Japan and USA).

Figure 3. Venn diagram depicting the different sectors, groups, categories and/or types of members of the SSAB, as well as the project’s stakeholders at large

2. Management and coordination activities during the first year of EUROqCHARM

2.1. Management Procedures

NIVA as coordinator is responsible for all financial, contractual and administrative aspects of project management defined by the Grant Agreement. To ensure a smooth and easy-going periodic reporting for all partners involved, NIVA has initiated and implemented a simplified internal periodic reporting framework, to help all project partners take stock of their progress towards EUROqCHARM overall objectives and deliverables, as well as to identify and mitigate potential risks and bottlenecks; and additionally, to make sure that there are no inconsistencies between the performed activities and the use of resources reported.

The internal reporting procedure has been put in place starting with Month 6, when project partners have been requested to provide the PM with their first simplified overview of the activities carried out from Month 1 – Month 6. Having an internal reporting at every 6 months is meant to ease the period technical report due in Month 18 which can be a daunting task, especially for project partners with little or no experience with the EU SyGMA portal reporting system, as well as for those partners involved simultaneously in multiple EU projects.

To this end, the NIVA Management Committee has developed a template and a procedure to support project partners in reporting easily and efficient their progress and activities.

2.2. Project Meetings

2.2.1. NIVA Management Committee Routine Meetings

The NIVA Management Committee established weekly administrative status meetings to facilitate smooth management of the project. The meetings follow the same structure every week, whereby the PC, PM, and PS share updates and plans for the following week, discuss priority topics, project timelines, task lists, the joint EUROqCHARM email account and any other business. These meetings are often followed by breaking out into individual tasks. Additional NIVA Management Committee members attended these meetings on an “as and when needed” basis in line with the progress and project requirements.

Tools and documents developed to support this process include an internal private NIVA Microsoft Teams channel and task lists in Excel. Most of these meetings were held online using Microsoft Teams until COVID-19 restrictions allowed in-person meetings (i.e., in autumn 2021).

2.2.2. Preparation and Organisation of Kick off Meeting (KOM) – November 2020

Preparations for the KOM began in September 2020, following the signing of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

Giving the global pandemic, COVID-19, the KOM was arranged as a virtual event. The NIVA Management Committee chose Microsoft Teams as the platform to facilitate the meeting. Following internal discussion and in consultation with WPLs, it was decided that the KOM meeting should be kept short and concise to avoid participant fatigue and a less productive/effective meeting. During the consultation rounds, several project partners had reported draining experiences from other virtual KOMs that exceeded six hours or fell over multiple days.

The purpose of the KOM was to set up good working routines among all partners; to this end, the meeting was structured in a concise way with a focus on the practicalities needed to initiate a collaborative working environment in all WPs. Taking these factors into consideration, the meeting was planned to be three hours long. The KOM was followed by several shorter meetings for each WP to arrange formalities and plans moving ahead. SC and SAB meetings were also separately held.

Partners were informed about the KOM date in October 2020 along with a preliminary agenda (Table 9). All partners were requested to prepare a single page PowerPoint slide for introductory purposes using a template (Figure 4). Partners were asked to deliver this to the NIVA Management Committee a week before the KOM. WPLs were asked to prepare a short (max 15 min) presentation for the KOM with support of their TLs using a template (Figure 5). Each WPL was requested to cover the following aspects: WP overview; task by task overview; main outcomes; dependencies on other WPs; timeline; next steps. WPLs were asked to deliver this to the NIVA Management Committee a week before the KOM.

The NIVA Management Committee put together all partners’ presentations into a single file to support a smooth dialogue/interaction during the virtual meeting. This allowed all participants to focus on the topics presented during the meeting and not being distracted by any technicalities (e.g., screen sharing).

The agenda for the KOM was prepared in advance by the NIVA Management Committee and circulated to all participants two weeks before the event. The KOM took place Thursday, 12th November 2020 from 09:00-12:00 CET. The meeting was organized for project partners only. The meeting was attended by 37 participants representing all 15 partners. The meeting was recorded with the consent of all participants. Presentations and minutes from the meeting were circulated to all participants for approval before being archived along with means of verification to complete the project’s first milestone (Milestone 1 – Kick off meeting). All documents are stored on the Microsoft Teams channel and awaiting migration to Zenodo.

Table 9. EUROqCHARM Kick Off Meeting Agenda

Agenda item	Responsible
Welcome / Presentation of EUROqCHARM	PC, PM
Presentation by EUROqCHARM Project Officer	Erik Pentimalli
Presentation of the partners	Partner PIs
Presentations of each WPs	WPLs
EUROqCHARM brand identity	ILVO
Project management and coordination	NIVA Management Committee
Questions and closing of the meeting	PC, PM

Norwegian Institute of Water Research

- Research institute focused on oceans and freshwater/catchment systems
- EUROqCHARM team based in Oslo, Norway
- Coordinator, leading WP6 and contributes to all WPs
- Leading the Norwegian Ships of Opportunity Program (NorSOOP) and Drone-based research, mapping, and monitoring in the coastal zone (SeaBee) national research infrastructures, participant in ICOS-OTC
- Participating in several relevant H2020 projects: INTAROS, JERICO-S3 (WP lead), DCS4COP, NAUTILUS

Bert van Bavel
Coordinator
WP 6
(WP2, WP4, WP5)

Amy Lusher
Project Manager
WP 6
(WP1, WP3, WP5)

Valentina Tartiu
(WP 4, 5, 6)

Inga Fløisand
EU Advisor

Liv R. Lang-Ree
Project support
responsible

Ståle Mygland
Financial controller

Figure 4. Example of introductory slide at KOM

<p style="text-align: center;">EUROqCHARM – KOM</p> <h2 style="text-align: center;">Work Package 2</h2> <p style="text-align: center; color: green;"><i>Validation of methods for plastics analysis in environmental samples</i></p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">Lead: VUA – Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Partners: CSIC, EAWAG, NIVA, Chiron, NILU, AFNOR, IFREMER)</p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">Kick off meeting 12th November 2020</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">EUROqCHARM – KOM</p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">Main Outcomes – Deliverables</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.1 Evaluation results interlaboratory study (Month 21, VUA) • D2.2 Feasibility study of harmonised protocol for use in large scale monitoring programs (Month 22, NIVA) • D2.3 Production of <i>at least</i> two CRMs, and identification of two candidate CRMs (Month 36, VUA)
<p style="text-align: center;">EUROqCHARM – KOM</p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">Task by task overview</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 2.1 Report on possibilities and needs for candidate CRMs for plastics in different matrices (water, air, biota and sediments) • Task 2.2 Producing analytical standard candidate CRM, and candidate matrix CRMs • Task 2.3 Organising one or more intercalibration studies using the candidate CRM • Task 2.4 Statistical validation of the ILC results • Task 2.5 Feasibility study of the methods for monitoring studies in terms of analytical uncertainty, applicability and costs • Task 2.6 Certification of reference materials 	<p style="text-align: center;">EUROqCHARM – KOM</p> <h3 style="text-align: center;">WP2 Time line</h3>

Figure 5. Example of WP presentation at KOM

2.2.3. SAB meetings

An initial meeting with the SAB members was held on the 11th November in advance of the KOM to facilitate the participation of SAB members who could not attend the EUROqCHARM KOM. This meeting was arranged to introduce each member of the SAB to the project aims and objectives (Table 10). The agenda and a description of the project was circulated to all SAB members in advance. The meeting was held through Microsoft Teams. After the meeting, a PDF of the presentation was shared with all SAB members; the PM initiated assigning each SAB member to WP(s) and deliverables according to each members’ field of expertise and interests

Table 10. EUROqCHARM Scientific Advisory Board meeting agenda

Agenda item	Responsible
Welcome / Presentation of EUROqCHARM	PC, PM
Presentations of each WP	PM
Role of stakeholders	PC
Questions and closing of the meeting	PC, PM

2.2.4. WP meetings

The main WPs active during the first year of the project were WP1, WP2, WP5 and WP6. All meetings held were arranged by WPLs or TLs responsible and most of them were held online due to the COVID-19 restrictions. NIVA’s PS assisted WPLs to run virtual meetings when requested, this included setting up calendar invitations through Microsoft Teams, taking minutes and circulating minutes to attendees.

The WP1 Workshop held 11-12 October 2021 (Milestone 5) was the first WP meeting to take place in-person. As described in Section 2.2.6, the WP1 Workshop was originally planned to be a part of a three-day event, as all partners would have been gathering in-person for the Annual Meeting. The initial plan was to include the WP1 Workshop in this three-day event to cut down on the project’s CO2 emissions. As it became necessary to split up the events, discussion and planning began for an in-person workshop. The WPL and TLs stressed the importance of having an in-person event, as the WP had suffered from “virtual meeting fatigue”. At the time, COVID-19 situation in Europe had improved sufficiently enough that a small, in-person event could be made possible.

It was decided that the WP1 Workshop take place at NIVA Denmark in Copenhagen, for the following reasons:

- Relatively central option in Europe for all WP1 Workshop participants to travel on shorter notice
- Access and availability of meeting rooms for the needed number of participants to gather
- Quick and easy access to video conferencing equipment allowing for a hybrid event (Figure 6 demonstrates how the event was hybrid)
- Availability of catering options on site which ensured steady workflow
- Local knowledge through employees at NIVA Denmark

Figure 6. Demonstrating the video conferencing equipment available at NIVA Denmark for the WP1 Workshop

2.2.5. Ad-hoc meetings with Stakeholders / SSABs

During the first six months of the project the PC and PM held several online meetings with stakeholders who had an interest in participating as SSAB members. The stakeholders included representatives from environment agencies, instrument manufacturers, international organisation involved in monitoring activities and standardisation bodies. These meetings were arranged to inform on the project plans and explain how EUROqCHARM would interact with SSAB members. An in-person stakeholder event was in the processes of being planned in connection to the EUROqCHARM 1st Annual Meeting. However, due to the COVID-19 restrictions, this was no longer feasible, and this event was postponed until November 2021 (see Section 2.2.6 for further information).

2.2.6. Preparation and Organisation of Annual Meeting – October 2021

Preparations for the Annual Meeting began in May 2020 with internal meetings amongst NIVA's Management Committee (Table 11). Once the scoping was complete, several small meetings were held in different teams to build plans and map activities. The original plan was to have a three-day event in October combining the WP1 Workshop (Milestone 6), Annual Meeting and General Assembly, and Stakeholder meeting. A "Save the Date" email was circulated to all project partners in June 2021.

In August 2020, it became clear that it was not going to be possible to hold the Annual Meeting in-person, as originally planned. The ongoing COVID-19 restrictions in Norway limiting the number of people at events, the requirement for full vaccination, and possible quarantine when traveling, deemed it necessary to re-evaluate plans. SC members were contacted with a proposition from the NIVA Management Committee to split the three days of the Annual Meeting into separate events, with the WP1 Workshop being the only event still in-person and the Annual Meeting/General Assembly and Stakeholder Meeting carried out online. Agreement was reached from all SC members and a decision was made to separate the components. All partners were informed on the 25th August.

Simultaneously, delays in WP1 caused by COVID-19 impacted progress across activities; meaning it was necessary to move Milestone 5 to October and delay Milestone 6. NIVA's Management Committee held meetings with each WPL to identify the risks associated with changes to the plans and future activities between in August and September 2021.

A calendar invitation and agenda for the Annual Meeting was circulated in September 2021 and project partners were given the opportunity to add items to the agenda by written notification up to 14 calendar days preceding the meeting. The invitation also included a copy of virtual meeting etiquette.

The Annual Meeting was held on 21st October 2021 with 38 participants including 2 SAB members.

Table 11. List of meetings and key decisions made leading up to the Annual Meeting

Date	Meeting purpose	Key decisions	Present
07.05.2021	Preparation for Annual Meeting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location requirements - Agenda items - Key activities: WP1 Workshop, Annual meeting, Stakeholder event, Synergies between WP1, WP2, WP3, General Assembly 	Importance of physical meeting if COVID-19 permits Breakout meetings for each aspect of the meeting	VT, BvB, AL, GH
21.05.2021	WP1 Workshop Planning <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify purpose and objectives for the WP1 Workshop. 2. Identify any decisions that need to be made at the WP1 Workshop. 3. Who should attend the WP1 Workshop? 4. What roles need to be assigned during the WP1 Workshop? 	Should the WP1 Workshop take place physically, digitally or hybrid?	BvB, SA, VT, AL, GH
21.05.2021	Preparation for General Assembly	Mapping of activities and participants	VT, BvB, AL, GH
27.05.2021	Preparation for the Stakeholders meeting	Mapping of activities and participants	VT, BvB, AL, GH
15.06.2021	EUROqCHARM Annual Meeting Preparation and mind-mapping session utilizing the Whiteboard application in Microsoft Teams	Mapping of activities and participants	BvB, AL, VT, GH
10.08.2021	Discussion for need to go virtual divide activities	Contact all WPLs for input	AL, BvB, GH
18.08.2021	EUROqCHARM Stakeholder engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More detailed definition of stakeholder types - Identification of both what stakeholders want and project needs 	Early development of the Stakeholder Strategy and mapping towards the Stakeholder meeting	AL, VT, GH
20.08.2021	WP1 Workshop discussion. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meeting to be separated from Annual Meeting and moved forward. 	Need for in-person meeting is high. Follow COVID rules per country. Responsibility back to WP1	AL, GH
26.08.2021	Stakeholder mind-mapping		BvB, AL, JF
01.09.2021	Annual Meeting Schedule	Drafted agenda for Annual Meeting	AL, GH
01.09-17.09.2021	Meeting to identify the risks associated with changes to the plans		AL, BvB plus PIs

2.3. EUROqCHARM Microsoft Teams

Once NIVA was informed that the EUROqCHARM proposal had been granted funding, the NIVA Management Committee set up a dedicated platform through Microsoft Teams to ensure quick, smooth and efficient communication among all project partners. Thus, the EUROqCHARM Microsoft Team was organized as such – a **General Channel** – aimed to cover the broader aspects of the project and to enable the exchange of information and files relevant for various partners involved, while

distinct channels for each WP were established to allow partners to get into more in-depth conversations and files exchange concerning the respective WPs, as well as to easily coordinate the WPs progress.

During the KOM, partners have been provided with an introduction and specific guidelines on the use of EUROqCHARM Microsoft Teams communication tool (see Figure 7). All partners have been encouraged to share the relevant documents via Teams dedicated channel and to work on “live” documents created by project partners in the various WPs/Tasks. Regular updates and support on the use of this tool is provided by NIVA’s PS, that is supervising the good functioning of it.

Figure 7. Excerpt of the Guidelines provided to project partners on the use of Microsoft Teams

2.4. Development of the Project Handbook

The EUROqCHARM Project Handbook (hereafter “the handbook”) was created to support project partners for the entire duration of the project. The purpose of the handbook is to provide guidance to EUROqCHARM partners about how to ensure smooth implementation of the project activities and comply with the needs of the H2020 programme execution framework. The handbook is subject to routine updates, according to the progress and requirements of the project (Figure 8).

The handbook identifies the procedures related to project management, project execution and communication. The goal of this handbook is to identify - for each of the operational needs of the project - roles, procedures and best practices in order to develop a clear approach for supporting partners throughout the development of the project. For this reason, the document has been divided into four main sections covering project management processes, project implementation routines, communication procedures, and templates to be used by partners throughout the project.

Figure 8. Excerpt from EUROqCHARM Project Handbook

The project management processes part of the handbook aims to guarantee a straightforward coordination of the activities resulting in high quality project outputs (e.g. deliverables, publications). To this end, it includes an overview of the project management structure, encompassing different levels of organization, as well as corresponding contact persons, responsible for the different roles defined within the Consortium Agreement and Annex I to the Grant Agreement.

When it comes to project implementation, the handbook covers aspects like monitoring progress, performance monitoring, financial reporting, risk assessment, quality assurance for EUROqCHARM deliverables, etc.

The communication procedures part of the handbook focuses on (i) internal communication good practices, aiming to set up a good internal communication strategy to ensure a clear and effective communication among partners, that allows recognising early escalation and the timely resolution of management and technical issues; (ii) external communication routines and processes to ensure a consistent, coherent presentation of the project to the public audience as well as to enable reaching a widest range of stakeholders and end-users.

The final part of the handbook puts forward a series of templates meant to support all the activities (see Section 2.5).

2.5. Development of the Project Templates

Project templates have been developed as part of the project management tools to facilitate the management of the project between all partners involved. All partners are asked to use them appropriately to ensure correct monitoring of actions and timely preparation of deliverables.

For example, all deliverables must be prepared in Word format using the pre-defined template, be written in English and proofread using spell check. When submitting the final deliverable, it must be converted into PDF format before uploading. Figure 9 and Figure 10 show examples of templates for deliverables and meeting minutes in Word format, respectively. Figure 11 shows an example of the 6-month/per-partner reports template in Excel format.

Figure 9. Example of deliverable template in Word format

Figure 10. Example of meeting minutes template in Word format

Figure 11. 6-month/per-partner report template in Excel format

2.6. Progress Monitoring

The assessment of the performance and success of the project will be directly and continuously performed by the PC and the PM and will be reported in a continuous and periodic matter to the Commission. An internal reporting procedure has been implemented to keep track of the project activities and identify potential risks and associated mitigation measures, this procedure encompasses the three-month status report per WP, six-month partner report, and annual reports as described below:

- **3-month/per-WP status reports:** This is a brief report about the technical progress, results obtained and compliance with the work programme. These are delivered by each WPL to the PM. The PM has been responsible to collect and process the reports ahead of the SC, and if needed, is taking the corrective actions in project work (i.e., to identify delays, changes, etc. if required).
- **6-month/per-partner reports,** in which each partner communicates the on-going activities (tasks and financial) within the project and points out any relevant issue. Per-partner reports must be strictly sent within seven calendar days from the deadline. These are delivered by the partner primary contact to the PM.
- **6-month reports:** - WPLs are compiling six-monthly and annual reports on the WP progress. WPLs are consolidate the activities within their WPs with contributions from partners (based on per-partner reports). These reports are further integrated into a project comprehensive report by the PM to highlight change in strategy, issues with project partners and involved key personnel, project results and resources, risk analysis, as well as growth of the stakeholder community. The PM is verifying the project results communicated in the 6-month WP reports against the evaluation plan, quality assurance plan and dissemination plan.
- **Annual reports:** WPLs submit a summary of progress report showing the technical changes carried out during the year. The PM will then prepare a consolidated progress report for all partners while the FO prepares a consolidated overview of the budgetary situation of the project based on the financial statements received from partners.

2.7. Financial Reporting

Financial management procedures developed within EUROqCHARM include coordinating all transactions between the European Commission (EC), the PC and other project partners, as well as overseeing reporting on project financial status. Financial and management reporting has been planned to be continuously controlled and delivered to the EC in the two 18-month reporting periods as required for H2020 projects and defined in the Grant Agreement. Deviations or additional budget needs will be reported to the PC and SC.

2.8. Quality Assurance for Deliverables

A high level of quality is essential to ensure the success of EUROqCHARM's implementation. Many deliverables of the project are and/or will be available to the public and can also be accessed long after the project's completion. The Quality Assurance plan has been created to maximise the impact and success of EUROqCHARM. The plan rests on timely deliverable preparations by all partners involved.

EUROqCHARM partners responsible for deliverables follow the agreed format for timely approval of all deliverables for submission. For deliverables that do not take the form of a written report, a written record is prepared to include supporting materials for the accomplishment.

Each deliverable is subject to reviews before being released and submitted to the European Commission. The following procedure has been developed for the internal review process:

- 1) When a deliverable is ready for circulation, the document shall be made available, through Microsoft Teams to the relevant Consortium members, who will then be informed via email by the WPL and who will have one week to provide their comments to the WPL.
- 2) The WP will address any received comments and inform the PM that it is ready for review by SC (WPLs), or SABs where relevant.
- 3) The PM is responsible for working with the WP leader to assign suitable reviewers, and will circulate the request for review, ensuring the reviewers are given at least 2 weeks to provide their feedback.
- 4) The reviewers will have the responsibility of determining the acceptability of the deliverable content and will return comments to the WPL within two weeks.
- 5) The WPL will then have one more week to finalise the deliverable in accordance with the comments made by the reviewers.
- 6) The last week before the deadline, the WP leader will send the deliverable to the PM who will finalise the deliverable before sending it to the PC, who will make final adjustments and send it to the PO.

In the case of disputes with the deliverable the advice of the Scientific Advisory Board will be sought.

TLS are responsible to deliver their task and associated deliverables to the WPL responsible. WPLs are responsible for checking that a deliverable will be achieved on time by TL and report to PM and PC if any delay is foreseen. The SC will review the deliverable before deliverables are sent, by the PM, to SABs for external review where appropriate. Both SC and SABs may return deliverables for additional refinement if they feel this necessary. Lastly, deliverables will be transmitted to the EC by the PC (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Workflow for quality assurance of EUROqCHARM deliverables

3. EUROqCHARM Coordination Activities with Relevant Working Groups and Ongoing Initiatives

In the first year of the project, EUROqCHARM project partners actively engaged with activities outside of the core project, aiming at discussing synergies and potential contributions that EUROqCHARM can bring during its implementation period. All partners agreed that the coordination activities with relevant working groups and ongoing initiatives at European and international level is of utmost importance for the achievement of EUROqCHARM goals. Thus, EUROqCHARM project was introduced to the various working groups and ongoing initiatives by means of customized presentations to suit the audience and to facilitate the discussion on synergies and potential contributions.

A general EUROqCHARM presentation was used for many of the meetings, with modifications to suit the audience. A copy of the general presentation is included in Appendix 1: Related Documents.

3.1. Activities Related to the European Commission Initiatives

3.1.1. H2020 Cluster Meetings

Cluster meeting on Projects Dealing with “Marine Litter – 1st June 2021

The PC attended an online cluster meeting organised by the European Research Executive Agency (REA): REA Unit B.3 “Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment”. Figure 13 shows an example excerpt from Bert van Bavel’s (PC) presentation at the Cluster meeting.

The purpose of this meeting was to bring together the project coordinators of 8 projects dealing with marine litter from different angles including (1) providing harmonisation of procedures for plastic pollution monitoring and assessments (EUROqCHARM), (2) providing sustainable alternatives to plastics currently used for different applications ([SEALIVE](#), [BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE](#)), or (3) developing technologies to remove litter and (micro)plastics from the oceans and seas ([CLAIM](#), [GoJelly](#), [MAELSTROM](#), [In-No-Plastic](#), [LABPLAS](#)).

The objectives of the workshop were: (i) to explore synergies and promote clusters activities between projects, (ii) to allow a dialogue with the Policy Officers working in related fields to discuss about relevant policy aspects and (iii) for projects to demonstrate/ discuss their expected results and how can contribute to “Feedback to policy”. The overarching goal was to maximise the impact of the projects and help them to provide a better contribution to the targets set by the EC in terms of reducing plastic pollution and preserving seas.

This cluster meeting was attended by approximately 35 participants representing the projects (Project Coordinators), representatives of policy European Commission’s Directorate Generals (DGs), Project Officers from REA, senior Project Advisers working with the EMMF program from CINEA and a Project Officer from the Joint Research Centre (JRC).

The PC was specifically asked to focus on activities towards policy and monitoring. His presentation was followed by a Q&A session which focused on the need, importance, and feasibility of developing state-of-the-art methods that are largely agreed upon (both from policy-makers and innovators/academia/business community), and the work done by the EC JRC to produce reference materials to use as basis for the work on harmonization.

EUROqCHARM Deliverables related to policy

- D3.1 : Recommendations of procedures and methods for monitoring programs [m24]
- D3.2 : Optimization of monitoring strategies to improve the MSFD strategy [m30]
- D3.3 : Standard measuring procedures for policy and legislation (baselines and thresholds) [m34]
- D3.4 : Report on global database synchronization [m34]

Links with other projects/networks

EUROqCHARM's multi stakeholder platform represented by EMODNet, CEN, ISO, MSFD, GESAMP and AMAP.

Figure 13. Excerpt from Presentation given by Bert van Bavel (PC) at the Cluster meeting

Cluster Meeting projects contributing to the EU Plastics Strategy – 30th September 2021

The PC attended an online cluster meeting organised by the European Research Executive Agency (REA): REA Unit B.3 “Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment”. Figure 14 shows an example excerpt from Bert van Bavel’s (PC) presentation at the Cluster meeting – September 30, 2021.

The purpose of this meeting was to bring together the project coordinators of 11 projects which have aspects related to the EU Plastics Strategy including (1) transitions to the circular economy ([JUST2CE](#)), (2) tackling plastic pollution (EUROqCHARM, [LABPLAS](#)), (3) plastics in agriculture ([PAPILLONS](#), [MINAGRIS](#)), (4) improving the sorting, separation and recycling of composite and multi-layer materials ([MERLIN](#), [CIMPA](#), [Sol-Rec2](#), [CIRCULAR FoodPak](#)), and (5) circular systems in plastics, textiles and furniture sectors ([SCIRT](#), [CISUFLO](#)).

The objective of the meeting and special attention was paid to relevance of the projects to EU policy relevance and how the projects can contribute concretely to the targets/ measures of the EU plastics strategy. In addition, communication/ dissemination activities of interest for other projects or EC policy officers were highlighted. This cluster meeting was attended by approximately 60 participants representing the projects and the REA and EU policy makers from the relevant DGs: DG RTD, DG ENV, DG AGRI, and DG GROW.

As a follow up to this meeting, EUROqCHARM has been started discussion with LABPLAS on the production of small microplastic and nano plastics reference materials. This is relevant to the activities in WP2.

EU Policy relevance of the EUROqCHARM

How will you contribute to EU Plastics Strategy?

Plastics Strategy & Circular Economy Action Plan unintentional release of microplastics

- Labelling, standardization, certification and regulatory measures **verification needed**
- Harmonise **methods for measuring MPs** (tyres, textiles) + harmonised data of **microplastics concentrations in seawater**
- Close the gaps in scientific knowledge related to the **risk and presence of microplastics** (environment, drinking water, food)
- Circular Economy initiative on MP
 - **Measures to reduce the release of MP** in the environment

Which EU policies, legislation and initiatives are to be addressed?

- Restrict **intentionally added microplastics** under REACH **verification needed**
- **Unintentionally microplastics**: tyres durability, microfibers in textiles, **verification requirements needed** (labelling, certification)
- **Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive** (UWWTD): under revision, COM proposal 2022, **measuring of microplastics considered**
- **Sewage Sludge Directive** (SSD): revision by Q3 2022, requirements secondary material (agriculture) **measuring needs in future**
- **Environmental Quality Standards Directive** (ESQD): under revision (surface water & groundwater quality standards) **measuring of microplastics considered**
- **Marine Strategy Framework Directive** (MSFD): under revision, COM proposal by 2023, **thresholds for litter types harmonisation of methodology**
- **Drinking Water Directive** (DWD): a methodology on measuring microplastics in drinking water by adopting Delegated Act(s) **legally binding** January 2024

EUROqCHARM | Presentation REA-B.3 Cluster Meeting – Bert van Bavel – 30 September 2021

Figure 14. Excerpt from Presentation given by Bert van Bavel (PC) at the Cluster meeting

3.1.2. MSFD Technical Group Marine Litter

Online meeting – 22nd-23rd June 2021

The PC and PM were invited to attend the MSFG TGML meeting to present EUROqCHARM and listen to MSFD D10 policy updates, with an overview of international collaboration activities, including the ongoing work within Regional Action plans, OSPAR, HELCOM, MEDPOL and BSC (Baltic Sea Convention). This was the ideal opportunity for EUROqCHARM to interact with actions happening in Europe and identify how EUROqCHARM can support future activities within the TGML. EUROqCHARM partners François Galgani (IFREMER), Jakob Strand (AU), Matteo Vinci and Alessandra Giorgetti (OGS) were also present in their capacity in the MSFD TGML. The meeting was attended by about 35 participants.

MSFD Technical Group Marine Litter – Microlitter workshop – 26th -27th October 2021

EUROqCHARM scientists, François Galgani, Jakob Strand, Matteo Vinci and Eugenia Molina participated in the MSFD TGML Meeting, at Ispra in Italy. The focus of the meeting was on microplastic monitoring methods within the MSFD and data, to support the implementation of microplastic monitoring. The meeting also allowed EUROqCHARM and TGML to better defined how EUROqCHARM will link with MSFD/ TGML group, through a future back to back meeting on monitoring strategies.

3.1.3. Interactions with the Joint Research Council (JRC)

Collaboration agreement JRC Geel

JRC Geel was present at the kick-off of WP2 the 29th of January and collaboration on the production and certification of reference material was discussed. A specific ‘collaboration agreement’ between EUROqCHARM was discussed and a draft was presented at a follow up meeting the 5th of May. There was discussion around whom would be the legal representative for EUROqCHARM, it could be NIVA as lead beneficiary or the VUA University who are leading WP2 and would work together with JRC at the facility in Geel. A visit of the PC to the JRC facilities in Geel in September was cancelled due to COVID-19 restrictions to visit this facility. JRC Geel is also experiencing a large ‘back log’ and a large workload due to the closure of the facility during 2020 and partly in 2021. The implementation and signing of the collaboration agreement will be discussed at successive meetings in the end of 2021.

JRC Symposium - Challenges of microplastic analysis: Bridging state of the art and policy needs – 9th September 2021

The PC presented EUROqCHARM at the JRC workshop in connection with the presentation of the results of a QUASIMEME/NORMAN interlaboratory study (ILC) and participated in a panel discussion on future activities concerning ILC studies. The need for collaboration around different ILC initiatives was highlighted by several participants of the workshop in addition to harmonisation of reporting formats and validation of the ILC results. EUROqCHARM has organised follow up meetings with JRC and BAM (responsible for another ILC), and has been participating in EUROMET discussions on ILC for small microplastics and nano-plastics.

3.2. Activities Related to International Plastic Monitoring Initiatives

3.2.1. OSPAR Microplastic Expert Working Group (MPEG)

EUROqCHARM partners including the PM participate in the OSPAR MPEG to ensure that activities occurring within expert working groups towards monitoring and the implementation of methods are fed into the project, and from the project to the MPEG, in a timely and efficient manner. OSPAR MPEG meetings are held on a routine basis. As a follow up to these meetings relevant information is shared within the EUROqCHARM, specifically activities towards identifying suitable methods is taken to WP1, WP2 and WP3. The NIVA Management Committee and the SC will use this information to develop future collaborative activities linked to the progress across WP3 and WP4. Meetings such as these provide EUROqCHARM with the state of monitoring objectives as well as future requirements needed to fulfil European legislation.

Online Meeting - 14th January 2021

The aim of the meeting was to work towards the proposal for a candidate indicator on microlitter in sediments. The meeting was attended by 18 MPEG members and 6 guests. The PM is a member of the MPEG as a representative of Norway. She was asked to present the status of ILC studies on analysis of microplastics in different matrices. This also allowed her the opportunity to present the goals of EUROqCHARM. Jakob Strand (AU) was also present in his capacity as a MPEG member and representative for Denmark. Three representatives of EUROqCHARM project partner OGS were present as guests. Further meetings will be held and EUROqCHARM partners are encouraged to feed information back to the project as and when relevant. Information is being gathered by the NIVA Management Team to build an overview of the status of all activities within the EU as part of WP3.

3.2.2. Norwegian Environment Agency – Norwegian Seminar on Microplastics: Current Knowledge Status on Sources, Effects and Risk – 7th - 8th April 2021

The Norwegian Environment Agency held an online webinar/seminar on the ongoing work both nationally and internationally, including towards the EU. The seminar was open to participants from across Norway where the topics of presentations and breakout sessions covering efforts to identify and quantify sources of microplastics, their effects and risks within a Norwegian context. The PM presented EUROqCHARM under the context of monitoring efforts in Norway. There were 68 participants in total including representatives of EUROqCHARM project partners, SALT and NILU. Meetings such as these provide EUROqCHARM with an understanding of the requirements key stakeholders, such as environment agencies, need for methods harmonisation whilst informing on the most recent developments at a national level, in this case the Norwegian situation. Following meetings such as these the NIVA Management Committee will be able to address the status of monitoring at national levels towards the EU and inform project partners of challenges being faced by stakeholders. EUROqCHARM will be seeking similar actions with additional stakeholders responsible for national monitoring across Europe during the second year of the project.

3.2.3. Activities related to the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)

EUROqCHARM partners including the PM participate in the AMAP Litter and Microplastics Expert Group to ensure that activities occurring within expert working groups towards monitoring and the implementation of methods are fed into the project, and from the project to AMAP, in a timely and efficient manner. AMAP LMEG meetings are held on a routine basis. Some interactions of note include:

International Symposium on Plastics in the Arctic 2-9th March 2021

EUROqCHARM partners presented their expertise through a number of presentations and panel discussions at the International Symposium on Plastics in the Arctic, hosted by the Government of Iceland. A reoccurring theme throughout the 5-day online event was the need for harmonized approaches to monitoring plastic impacts in the Arctic. EUROqCHARM partners participated in discussions of requirements for harmonized methods and the development of monitoring methods currently being facilitated by AMAP.

Circumpolar workshop on Arctic Plastic Pollution - Science, knowledge and education - 12th April 2021

Hosted by the UArctic Thematic Network on Arctic Plastic Pollution in partnership with the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) and the Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment Working Group (PAME), this workshop aimed to develop transdisciplinary research ideas to address the knowledge gaps, and strengthen collaboration between the UArctic and relevant Arctic Council working groups and to improve knowledge about plastic pollution and implement measures to reduce plastic pollution in the Arctic. The PM was asked to present activities in AMAP towards harmonisation of methods, including gaps and priorities in science and knowledge.

Meetings such as these provide EUROqCHARM with an understanding of key stakeholder activities - such as international agencies activities - towards methods harmonisation whilst informing them on the most recent developments coming from within the EUROqCHARM project. Following meetings such as these the NIVA Management Committee can address the status of international activities which may impact similar activities within the EU and inform project partners of challenges being faced.

3.2.4. Ministry of Environment, Japan – International Expert Meeting on Marine Plastic Litter Monitoring Data Sharing Project

The Ministry of Environment, Japan (MOEJ) has established an expert panel addressing the aspects of sea surface plastic monitoring, and has published a Guideline (2020) for sampling, and sample treatment, using Manta net for surface sampling of floating marine litter (https://www.env.go.jp/en/water/marine_litter/guidelines/guidelines.pdf). Two EUROqCHARM members are part of the expert panel (François Galgani and Amy Lusher). The next steps in the MOEJ initiative are to address how global data sharing can be achieved through a common web portal where these data preferably should be accessible for all. This was relevant EUROqCHARM as the MOEJ has been addressing the issue of harmonisation specifically towards sea surface plastic monitoring. MOEJ is taking an active role in the international effort to help establish globally coordinated marine litter monitoring. These meetings allow EUROqCHARM insights into the activities occurring outside of Europe and may impact activities within Europe.

1st International Expert Meeting – 18th December 2020

The 1st International Expert Meeting on the marine plastic litter monitoring data sharing project was attended by the PM (Amy Lusher) along with WP3 leader, François Galgani. Both were invited experts

to the meeting. The meeting presenting international initiatives towards synchronisation of data from marine litter monitoring. The meeting was live translated into both English and Japanese to an audience of about 35 invited attendees.

2nd International Expert Meeting – 24th February 2021

The 2nd International Expert Meeting on the marine plastic litter monitoring data sharing project was attended by the PM (Amy Lusher) along with WP3 leader, François Galgani. Both were invited experts to the meeting. The PM presented EUROqCHARM. The meeting was live translated into both English and Japanese to an audience of about 35 invited attendees.

3.3. Activities Related to Standardisation Bodies

3.3.1. ISO/CEN

A fundamental aspect of EUROqCHARM activities is to follow closely the progress within international and European standardisation bodies. This is to ensure that information from within the project - on the latest developments in methods - are being accurately reflected within the many different technical committees working towards standards on the topic of plastics in the environment. The aim of EUROqCHARM in this regard is to support the flow of information gathered through activities such as being conducted in WP1 and WP2 and provide feedback to stakeholders working on method development on the requirements for standards development. The belief is that EUROqCHARM can support the accelerate adoption of developed standards aligning with guidelines being developed through EU policy and legislation. It is therefore very important the activities of EUROqCHARM are clearly visible to as many of the active technical committees as possible. The EUROqCHARM project is represented by various participants in the working groups of ISO International Organisation for Standards (ISO) and CEN (European Committee for Standardization), including amongst others ISO/TC61 / SC 14 – Environmental aspects. Further, EUROqCHARM was presented in meetings for new and initial meetings of further working groups. The NIVA Management Committee will encourage partners to join their local standardisation bodies to implement the outcomes and recommendations of the project in upcoming European and international standards for the assessment of plastics of all sizes. Some of the meetings attended by EUROqCHARM partners are included next:

Online Meeting – 26th November 2020

The PC had a discussion and presentation with representatives from ISO/CEN on the role that EUROqCHARM can have towards the activities within standardisation of methods for plastic and microplastic analysis.

ISO/TC 147/SC 2 JWG – 30th - 31st March 2021

Within ISO a new working group on plastics was established on March 30th 2021. The work of this working group is very much in-line with EUROqCHARM because EUROqCHARM project partners will play an active role in the further development of standard methods within this working group of national experts. The PC presented EUROqCHARM and discussed several possibilities for collaboration. There were about 40 participants at this online meeting.

CEN European Workshop on Microplastics– 20th May 2021

The PC attended an online meeting organised by NEN (nen-evenementen.nl), the Royal Netherlands Standardization Institute. This workshop was organized on behalf of CEN/TC 444 'Environmental characterization of solid matrices'. Figure 15 shows an example excerpt from Bert van Bavel's (PC) presentation given at this meeting. The PC presented EUROqCHARM to about 370 participants. The seminar is available on the video sharing platform [vimeo](https://vimeo.com/584848484).

Summary

- EUROqCHARM will establish harmonized methodologies for the monitoring and assessment of macro-, micro- and nanoplastics in the environment with key actors involved in plastic pollution research in Europe
- EUROqCHARM will critically review state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonization one step further, validating these methods through interlaboratory comparison studies.
- EUROqCHARM will build European capacity for European environmental monitoring programmes on plastic pollution and produce reference materials in support of long-term quality control of analytical methods.

www.euroqcharm.eu

EUROqCHARM – Bert van Bavel – CEN TC 444 – 20th May 2021

Figure 15. Excerpt from Presentation given by Bert van Bavel (PC) at the CEN/TC 444 meeting

3.3.2. Standards Norway

Online Meeting 19th November 2020

The PC attended an online meeting organised by Standards Norway. The meeting was held in Norwegian and the PC presented EUROqCHARM to about 20 participants.

Norsk komité SN/K 153 Vannkvalitet – Online Meeting – 19th March 2021

The PC attended an online meeting organised by the Standards Norway committee on how the results from EUROqCHARM can be implemented in Norway. In addition, the possibility of developing Norwegian standards or blueprints for standardisation, which are not further developed at an international or European level (ISO/CEN) are of interest for a Norwegian setting. The meeting was held in Norwegian and the PC presented EUROqCHARM to about 35 participants. The PC continues to participate in national activities through Standards Norway.

3.4. Activities Related to Scientific Networks and the Scientific Community

3.4.1. NORMAN Network

The [NORMAN Network](#) is a network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances. Its purpose is to enhance the exchange of information on emerging environmental substances and encourage the validation and harmonisation of common measurement methods and monitoring tools so that the requirements of risk assessors and risk managers can be better met. It specifically seeks both to promote and to benefit from the synergies between research teams from different countries in the field of emerging substances. The working group on micro and nano materials is of special interest for EUROqCHARM and several EUROqCHARM partners are members of the NORMAN network or the working group. The NORMAN network has the outreach of more than 100 members in the field of environmental pollutants, organises workshops and supports collaborative action. EUROqCHARM engagement in these settings are important to spread knowledge of the project and gather input from expert scientists who are also involved in methods development, optimisation and harmonisation.

NORMAN WG4 Meeting – 17th November 2020

The PC co-chaired an online meeting for the Norman Network Working Group 4 – (Nano-and micro scale particulate contaminants). He gave a presentation of EUROqCHARM and related activities to the working group. There were about 30 participants at this meeting.

NORMAN Network General Assembly – 2nd December 2020

The PC attended the NORMAN General Assembly. EUROqCHARM was represented by a pre-recorded presentation from the PM which was accessible via an interactive web platform (see example in Figure 16). At the end of the meeting the presentation had been viewed by 154 participants. The PC also took part in a discussion and was leading a session. This generated a lot of interest in EUROqCHARM’s work on reference materials, ILC studies, and the harmonisation of analytical methods. EUROqCHARM through the PC and partner Ralf Kägi took part in the discussions of NORMANs Joint Project Initiatives (JPI). A JPI supporting WP2 is planned to be submitted for 2022 to support a workshop and other dissemination activities within the NORMAN network and the micro and nanoplastic Working Group.

Figure 16. Screenshot of EUROqCHARM presentation accessible via the NORMAN Network General Assembly online platform

3.4.2. Micro2020 23-27th November 2020

[Micro2020](#) was an international conference on the “*Fate and Impacts of Microplastics: Knowledge and Responsibilities*”. The event was held online. The PM pre-recorded a presentation to introduce EUROqCHARM to the scientific community. 51 people listened to the presentation live on the 25th November 2020 and the presentation was followed by a Q&A session. Several other EUROqCHARM partners attended the virtual meeting which also show-cased the diversity in microplastic research around the world. There were over 2000 authors and 500 individual communications.

3.4.3. SETAC Seminar Series – Microplastics in Humans and the Environment

The SETAC Seminar Series ran between 16th March to 6th April and consisted of 7 virtual Key Note Seminars covering the topic “**What We Know and What We Need To Know: The Analysis, Monitoring and Effects of Microplastics in Humans and the Environment**”.

EUROqCHARM researchers Sebastian Primpke (AWI) and Amy Lusher (NIVA, PM) are Steering Committee members of the SETAC IG on Microplastics. As part of their role they organised and co-chaired the seminar series (see examples from their presentations in Figure 17). EUROqCHARM was included in Seminar 1: Welcome & Introduction: State of the Science (Presentations, Lusher and Primpke), Seminar 2: Finding the Needle in the Haystack: Sampling, Extraction and Analysis of Microplastics (Chair – Primpke); Seminar 3: Towards the Harmonized Identification of Microplastics (Chair – Lusher, Primpke). Specifically, the Panel in Seminar 3 focused on bridging the gap between research, harmonization, and policy needs. EUROqCHARMs PC, Bert van Bavel, represented the project in the panel discussion. The broad audience attending SETAC meant that the activities of the project were highlighted to many stakeholders, including those from academia, industry and policy. Based on feedback gathered during the sessions and panel discussions, the NIVA Management Committee were able to identify similar harmonization activities being conducted outside of Europe, broaden the EUROqCHARM project network and to begin discussions on future collaborations.

Figure 17. Screenshot of EUROqCHARM activities during the SETAC Special Science Symposium

3.4.4. SETAC EUROPE Annual Meeting – 4th May 2021

Sebastian Pimpke (AWI) and Amy Lusher (NIVA) co-chaired a session during the SETAC Europe Annual Meeting. “3.08 – Harmonized data reporting and analyses in micro- and nanoplastics research with a discussion session on Tuesday 4th May, 13:15 – 14:15 CEST”. This session was specifically crafted to support activities in EUROqCHARM and inform the European/international scientific community of the project. The PC along with EUROqCHARM WP leaders presented a status of their work and participated in a live discussion session. A poster of EUROqCHARM was also made available to describe the project (Figure 18). There were over 150 participants to the session. As an outcome of this activity EUROqCHARM broadened its network and attracted additional interested stakeholders. This activity was successful and the EUROqCHARM Management Committee is encouraging similar dissemination activities to support knowledge sharing of project results (WP5), to engage with researchers working with state-of-the-art methods (for WPs1, 2, 4), and the implementation of monitoring (for WP3).

EUROCHARM
European Quality Controlled Harmonization
Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution

Standardization of methods to measure plastic pollution by 2024?
EUROqCHARM faces up to the challenge

@EUROqCHARM
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EUROqCHARM will use a multi-stakeholder approach to identify and develop cost-effective monitoring strategies for plastics (nano-, micro-, macro-) in all environmental matrices.

EUROqCHARM will facilitate developments for European plastic monitoring programmes and the realization of international best-practices.

Goals:	How?	Why?	EUROqCHARM will deliver the necessary methodological harmonization to successfully implement long-term strategies for combating plastic pollution.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a platform to discuss and validate methods for monitoring of plastics in environmental samples. Develop blueprints for standardization. Recommend revision of current EU policies and instruments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EUROqCHARM will evaluate existing methods for the assessment of plastic pollution. Harmonize these methods on a European level - with rigorous quality control - and reinforce European monitoring capacities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Major actions to evaluate, optimize and harmonize monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution are urgently needed. This will support substantial improvements in international environmental sustainability and socio-economic development 	<p>Scan to access www.euroqcharm.eu and sign up for our newsletter!</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 coordination and support action under grant agreement No. 101000805 (EUROqCHARM). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Figure 18. EUROqCHARM Poster prepared for SETAC meeting

3.5. Activities Related to Industry

3.5.1. ThermoFischer

The PC had a discussion with a representative from ThermoFischer on the role they can play as an industrial stakeholder within the EUROqCHARM project. These meetings lead to fruitful engagement and the invitation to attend the ThermoFischer Scientific Science for Sustainability Symposium.

3.5.2. Perkin Elmer Global Environmental Summit – 4th June 2021

This was a virtual event to provide an opportunity for the environmental science community to discuss aspects emerging contaminants, as well as microplastics and plastics, amongst other topics. The PC presented EUROqCHARM in a presentation entitled “In Search of the Quality of Micro Plastics Analysis”. There were 70 attendees to the live discussion with over 1300 registrations to the summit. Perkin Elmer are an industry representative which manufacture analytical instruments used for microplastic analysis. Thus, their engagement at a stakeholder level is important to the project.

4. Critical Implementation of Risks and Mitigation Actions

As part of the management procedures a Risk Register was developed during the project initiation phase. The Risk Register is a log of any issue which arises during the project. The PM has the responsibility to have an overview of the risk management of the project and to discuss the risk assessments with the SC. Risks are constantly evaluated by the PM and NIVA Management Committee depending on the severity of consequences and chance of happening.

It is the role of the PM to sort and assign the actions to items raised on the Risk Register with the support of the SC and ensure that the actions are followed up. However, it is the role of all consortium members, third parties and User Group members to raise issues and present them to the PM.

4.1. Overcoming Restrictions of COVID-19

The EUROqCHARM project has kicked-off amid the COVID-19 global pandemic and, thus, had to reconsider the implementation of several activities planned for the first year of project, while seeking to minimize the potential detrimental effects of switching from on-site meetings and events to the virtual settings.

To this end, NIVA Management Committee has put in place a system meant to support all project partners that had to cope with the COVID-19 restrictions while implementing their very first activities in the respective WPs.

Thus, NIVA Management Committee gave a high priority to the establishment and organisation of the EUROqCHARM communication platform – i.e., the EUROqCHARM Microsoft Teams as the frontend (presented in Section 2.3) and SharePoint as the backend.

In addition, NIVA through its PS has ensured that partners who are less familiar with this type of virtual communication platform benefit from intermittent in-house training and ongoing support on a “when needed” basis/at partners' request. This is especially due to some challenges reported in the very first months of the project's implementation, for example:

1. Project partners already utilising Microsoft Teams at their organisation had trouble logging in to NIVA's Microsoft Teams system (i.e., tenant)
2. Project partners failed to provide and/or were not aware of the email associated with their Microsoft Office account for NIVA to correctly add the right email

A solution to the first challenge was discovered by sharing links to documents and files in the EUROqCHARM Microsoft Team via SharePoint. This method of opening documents via SharePoint (i.e., the backend for Microsoft Teams) in a browser has since been encouraged for all project partners if they encounter any issues. This loophole allows for project partners to stay logged into their organisations' Microsoft Teams tenant whilst also accessing project documents on NIVA's tenant.

The establishment of the EUROqCHARM Teams platform has enabled a smooth transition towards the organization of all scheduled meetings in the virtual setting. Thus, the kick-off meeting, General Assembly meetings, as well as regular meetings of different management bodies, e.g., the SC, have been successfully organized through Teams under the COVID-19 global pandemic restrictions throughout the first year of the project. Although originally planned to be held in person also the EUROqCHARM Annual Meeting had to be rethought and organized in the virtual setting.

4.2. WP 1 – Workshop on Critical Revision of RAPs and SWOTs

One risk identified to have potentially far-reaching consequences on the project was the restrictions imposed on WP1 due to the global COVID-19 pandemic. The WP had originally been designed with in-person meetings and workshops forming the foundations of the collaborative, systematic tasks within the WP. The COVID-19 pandemic meant that all the vital planning phases and implementations steps for the WP had to be conducted through virtual meetings. One of the consequences was delays in tasks due to the demand for online meetings which extended outside the project. All project partners recognised the pressure the situation was putting on the tasks and a major effort was made to align one of the workshops (Milestone 5) with the Annual Meeting to allow for a more fruitful, in-person interaction (Section 2.2.6). When the Annual Meeting was changed to an online event, the WPL and TLs (WP1) stressed the importance of having an in-person event, as the WP had suffered from “virtual meeting fatigue” and was at risk of not delivering on its priority tasks. Discussions were held between the NIVA Management Committee, WPL and TLs to assess the situation and find solutions to move the meeting forward and facilitate an in-person event. Country entry requirements and venues were assessed and by September 2021, the COVID-19 situation in Europe had improved sufficiently that a small, in-person event could be made possible. A central, mainland Europe venue, close to a transport hub was sought that could facilitate a hybrid event. More details on the workshop are presented in Section 2.2.4.

The consequence of holding the workshop in-person was a fruitful interaction, the generation of numerous results and action points, and importantly, alleviated some of the pressure on the tasks (T1-1-1.4). Following the meeting, a decision was made in accordance with the GeA and SC that the main deliverable associated with the task (D1.1) would be moved by six weeks. Dedicated WPL meetings will be held with the other WPs to define details of the impacts this will have on the other WPs. Lastly, Weekly (virtual) WP1 TL meetings are scheduled until the deliverable due date.

5. Conclusion

The project management activities, procedures and tools developed and implemented during the first year of the EUROqCHARM project have enabled a smooth implementation of the project. The establishment of tools has allowed the project partners, Tls and WPLs to be efficient and flexible. In the remaining two years of the project, the tools developed will continue to be adjusted when and where deemed necessary by the EUROqCHARM Management Bodies/SC. This will allow for efficiency, flexibility, and openness within the project, and completion of the project in a realistic, and cost-effective manner with high-quality deliverables.

APPENDIX 1: RELATED DOCUMENTS

Appendix 1. Standard EUROqCHARM stakeholder presentation used in the first year of the project

<p>EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution</p> <p>Bert van Bavel/Amy Lusher Project Coordinator / Project Manager Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)</p> <p>Stakeholder Presentation.</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000805 (EUROqCHARM). This subject reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.</small></p>	<h4>Project Facts</h4> <p>EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution</p> <p>Horizon 2020 Call: H2020-CESC5-29-2020 Type of call: Coordination and Support Action (CSA) Project number: 101000805 Total budget: 2 045 000 € Project hours: 198.5 PM total Societal Challenge 5: Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials</p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>
<h4>EUROqCHARM Consortium</h4> <p>Lead Beneficiary: NIVA - Project Coordinator: Prof. Bert van Bavel Scientific Project Manager: Dr. Amy Lusher</p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>	<h4>Why EUROqCHARM:</h4> <p>Globally: Sustainable Development Goals 12, 14; UNEA Resolution 4.6</p> <p>SDG14.1: By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution</p> <p>Europe: EU Member States and Regional Sea Conventions must ratify monitoring frameworks and instruments; Marine Strategy Framework Directive; Water Framework Directive; EU Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy</p> <p>To reach substantial improvements in environmental sustainability and socio-economic development, it is essential to undertake major actions for the evaluation and optimization of plastic pollution monitoring and assessment.</p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>
<h4>EUROqCHARM Goal:</h4> <p>EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution</p> <p>EUROqCHARM's overarching goal is to provide a platform to discuss and validate methods for monitoring environmental samples for plastics, to develop blueprints for standards and to formulate recommendations for revision of current EU policies and instruments.</p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>	<h4>Concept</h4> <p>Support future strategic programming for research and innovation into plastic pollution monitoring and mitigation</p> <p><small>Legend: CRM: Certified Reference Material; TRL: Technological Readiness Level; if the TRL is < 3 protocols and methods are not further considered for the harmonisation process</small></p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>
<h4>WP 1 Screening and analysis of methods</h4> <p>Purpose: identify state-of-the art procedures for sample collection, sample preparation and analysis of plastics from environmental samples to define matrix- and size- adapted methods and the subsequent tasks within the following WPs.</p> <p>Key outputs: Compile existing methods used to quantify plastics in environmental matrices; Map protocol development; Evaluate their suitability requirement for further validation (WP2) or direct implementation (WP3);</p> <p>WP 2 Validation of methods</p> <p>Purpose: validate methods for use in the monitoring and assessment of plastics in environmental matrices to harmonise the sample workflow from preparation to analysis and data reporting.</p> <p>Main tasks: 1) Compare selected methods for plastic pollution monitoring - ILC study; 2) Develop protocols that can be used as standards for QA/QC validation; 3) Produce reference materials; 4) Facilitate infrastructure development across the measurement supply chain, standards developing organisation and end-users.</p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>	<h4>Associated Laboratories</h4> <p>LABORATORIES OUTSIDE OF EUROPE NOT SHOWN</p> <p><small>EUROqCHARM - Stakeholder Presentation - Amy Lusher - June 2021</small></p>

<p>WP 3 Harmonisation </p> <p>The purpose of WP3 is to internationally harmonise monitoring methods and data reporting so that they can be used by stakeholders to formulate and implemented policy and legislation.</p> <p>Main tasks: 1) Develop recommendations based on outputs from WP1 and WP2; 2) Present guidance on monitoring strategies; 3) Align European procedures with global strategies for data management and reporting.</p> <p>WP 4 Capacity Building </p> <p>WP4 has been specifically designed to facilitate the acceleration and adoption of developed standards and guidelines in member states by bringing together a critical mass of actors to draw synergies between environmental monitoring.</p> <p>Main tasks: 1) Establish an Operational Network for plastic monitoring; 2) Workshop facilitation; 3) Transnational Joint Actions.</p> <p> EUROQCHARM – Stakeholder Presentation – Amy Lueher – June 2021</p>	<p>WP 5 Knowledge Transfer and Dissemination </p> <p>WP5 cross-cuts all work packages to ensure that knowledge transfer and dissemination of project outputs reach the wider target audience of EUROQCHARM.</p> <p>Main tasks: 1) Brand identity; 2) Build and maintain collaborative relationships with stakeholders at various levels within the project; 3) Regularly share information through a dedicated website and social media channels; 4) Transfer knowledge of best practices concerning issues of plastic pollution monitoring via dedicated events.</p> <p>WP 6 Project Management and Coordination </p> <p>WP7 Ethics</p> <p> EUROQCHARM – Stakeholder Presentation – Amy Lueher – June 2021</p>
<p>Stakeholders</p> <p>A wide network of representatives will be established including international and national environment agencies and programs, regulatory authorities, monitoring networks, NGOs, standards bodies, industry representatives and instrument manufacturers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings once a year • One-to-one initiative meetings <p>Scientific Advisory Board</p> <p>Composed of 7 world-leading experts in aspects of nano-, micro- and macroplastic pollution with a complementary set of research backgrounds (UK, USA, China, S. Africa, Brazil, Canada, Australia)</p> <p>Including...</p> <p> EUROQCHARM – Stakeholder Presentation – Amy Lueher – June 2021</p>	<p>Summary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EUROQCHARM will use a multi-stakeholder approach to identify and develop cost-effective monitoring strategies for all environmental matrices and plastic sizes (nano-, micro-, macro-) • This innovative approach will bring together the existing plastic monitoring schemes within EU countries, at the EU and global levels. • EUROQCHARM will facilitate improvements in plastic monitoring programmes and the realization of international best-practices <p>EUROpean Quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution</p> <p> EUROQCHARM – Stakeholder Presentation – Amy Lueher – June 2021</p>
<p style="text-align: right;"></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Thank You</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Questions and enquiries:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">EUROQCHARM@niva.no @EUROQCHARM</p> <p><small>The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 cooperative and support action under grant agreement No. 101019910 (EUROQCHARM). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.</small></p> <p> EUROQCHARM – Stakeholder Presentation – Amy Lueher – June 2021</p>	

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